

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF FIBER-REINFORCED ELASTOMER COMPOSITES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Current phase of the study was undertaken to examine tensile fatigue behavior of fiber-reinforced elastomer composites representing bias aircraft tire carcass under various frequencies up to the level which closely simulates loading during high-speed take-off of aircraft. At a given stress amplitude, the use of higher cyclic frequency was found to affect strain response and heat build-up characteristics of composites significantly. The lower level of *initial strain* observed at higher frequency stems clearly from strain rate dependence of deformation of elastomer matrix composites. The temperature profile of the specimens subjected from 20 to 30 Hz loading showed that hysteretic heating under these conditions may lead to thermal fatigue failure as well as chemical degradation influencing both fiber-matrix adhesion strength and matrix strength. The involvement of material degradation process was indicated by the fact that gross failure of composites requires lower value of *dynamic creep* when the frequency is increased. At the same time, the use of higher frequency resulted in exponentially higher *dynamic creep rate*. For load range tested, the *energy loss per cycle* was found to be nearly constant and independent of the frequency. As a result, the *energy loss per unit time* became linearly proportional to the frequency. Since fatigue life of carcass composites is linearly proportional to the inverse of frequency, it was postulated that the rate of energy loss determines the lifetime of composites. The study revealed that the specimen surface temperature may not describe such critical parameters as internal heating particularly at the point of crack initiation or true heat dissipation rate.

KEY WORDS: Fiber-Reinforced Elastomers, Cord-Rubber Composites, Aircraft Tires, Fatigue, Life Prediction, Damage Accumulation, Delamination, Hysteresis, Heat Generation.

INTRODUCTION

As described in our previous papers (1-3), an initiative is underway to realign the aircraft tire test procedure where the emphasis is placed on more cost-effective and less empirical prediction of fatigue lifetime of tires. The operational life of aircraft tires is currently certified by costly dynamometer testing in which the tires are subjected to various combinations of speed and footprint load representing typical operating conditions in the field (4,5). Depending on the severity of loading conditions, cumulative damage is induced in critical regions of tires and eventually develops into catastrophic failure (5,6). For bias-ply aircraft tires, one of the most susceptible locations for damage initiation and accumulation has been the *carcass* (composite plies comprising a pressure vessel part of each tire) in the *shoulder* area. The dynamometer testing clearly provides an accelerated means of evaluating the structural durability and integrity of aircraft tires. However, the usefulness of dynamometer tests in current form is limited by their empirical nature. The test results reflect merely the sensitivity of each particular tire design and construction to a given set of loading conditions, unless underlying mechanisms of property degradation, damage accumulation and structural failure of tires are identified.

In implementing the proposed initiative, our research effort has been concentrated in defining the deformation and fracture mechanisms of angle-ply fiber-reinforced elastomer composite specimens which simulate the material elements of bias aircraft tire carcass in the shoulder area. The initial goal of our study is to identify the stress, strain or temperature parameters that control the process of fatigue damage accumulation for tire carcass composites under *uniaxial tension*, *biaxial tension*, *out-of-plane bending*, and *in-plane shear*. Eventually, it is hoped a fatigue law can be formulated that will serve to predict the life of the tire carcass on a more analytical basis and thereby to complement empirical nature of dynamometer tests. For a better determination of the failure modes, our study initially utilized the *model* composites reinforced by steel wire cables. Subsequently the research program included nylon fiber-reinforced composites which represent the actual *aircraft tire carcass*. Under uniaxial cyclic loading which represents fluctuating circumferential tension in the footprint region of tires, these angle-ply composite specimens were found to exhibit high level of interply shear deformation.

The interply shear deformation behavior of angle-ply composites were analyzed by a number of investigators in the past (1,2,7-13). Interply shear strain develops in angle-ply laminates when the constituent plies exhibit in-plane shear deformation of opposite direction but the action is prevented by mutual constraint due to interply bonding. Compared with the case of fiber-reinforced plastic composites (13), fiber-reinforced elastomer composites exhibit unusually high level of interply shear strain which results from the load-induced change of reinforcement angle allowed by extreme compliance of elastomer matrix. Our previous study (1) showed that, at an axial tensile strain of 10 percent, an interply shear strain of around 30 percent develops in the nylon fiber-reinforced composites representing the aircraft tire carcass with an initial reinforcement angle of ± 38 degree. Experimental study of the load-displacement response and interply shear strain variations was accompanied by detailed stress analysis based on finite element method (1,2). Linear elastic orthotropic or isotropic material elements were used for modeling. Our predictions were in reasonably good agreement with the experimental results.

Above a critical value of interply shear strain, these angle-ply composites were found to exhibit localized failure initiated in the form of *fiber-matrix debonding* as observed by other investigators (14,15). Debonding is started around the cut ends of fibrous cord reinforcements at the edge of the finite width coupons. This phenomenon is justified since the maximum interply shear strain occurs at the edge of the specimen. A new finding by our previous study (1,3) was that the critical load for the onset of fiber-matrix debonding constitutes a threshold level for semi-infinite fatigue life, i.e. *fatigue endurance limit*, of the composites. The physical meaning of an endurance limit is that, with cyclic stresses lower than this threshold, fiber-matrix debonding is never initiated nor developed. Under cyclic tensile stresses exceeding the endurance limit, fiber-matrix debonding was found to be progressively worsened and developed into *matrix cracking* and *delamination* leading to gross failure of the composites.

The damage accumulation in the forms of debonding, matrix cracking and delamination was accompanied by local strain increase (referred as *dynamic creep* hereafter), heat generation and acoustic emission (AE). The dynamic creep rate and the rate of temperature increase were inversely proportional to the fatigue life according to a power law (2). In monitoring of AE, distinctly different rates of signal accumulation could be assigned to the debonding and delamination failure modes (2). Our study examined the effects of different stress parameters on the fatigue resistance of composites to a limited extent (2,3). Among them, *stress amplitude* was found to play a dominant role in determining fatigue lifetime. When the minimum cyclic stress is near zero, the S-N (stress amplitude vs fatigue life) curve of the composites exhibits a steeper slope with shortened fatigue life in the normal loading range. However, the study was restricted to the case of low-frequency cyclic loading.

Reviewing the progress of our study so far, it is clear that more systematic efforts are needed to investigate the following two areas of interest for aircraft tire carcass composites: (a) the effects of stress, strain and temperature *history* on the fracture mechanisms particularly under high-frequency cyclic loading; (b) *monitoring* of damage accumulation process. Under high-frequency cyclic loading, heat build-up due to hysteretic nature of constituent materials may play more prominent roles in controlling the fatigue life of fiber-reinforced elastomer composites. Understanding of the subject will be an important step for the future study which plans to predict fatigue lifetime of

composites under complex sequences of load and frequency. Our study of fatigue mechanisms of tire carcass composites should also include the development of damage monitoring techniques as its integral part. When fully established, these experimental methodologies for damage monitoring are expected to be *in-situ* or *real-time* means of predicting residual life of tire carcass under fatigue loading. Within this context, our study has been expanded to examine tensile fatigue behavior of aircraft tire carcass composites under various frequencies up to the level which closely simulates loading during high-speed take-off of aircraft. The study has also assessed the effectiveness of the measurement of strain or temperature in monitoring of fatigue damage accumulation under high frequency. This paper reports preliminary findings of these efforts.

Objectives The present study was undertaken to investigate the effects of stress, strain and temperature history on the fracture mechanisms of aircraft tire carcass composites particularly under *high-frequency* cyclic loading and to assess the effectiveness of the measurement of strain or temperature in monitoring of damage accumulation process.

EXPERIMENTS

Angle-ply composite laminate specimens were prepared from the calendered plies used for construction of actual standard-grade carcass of *KC-135 aircraft tire*. The composite system was made of carbon black-filled proprietary rubber compound matrix and 1260/2 nylon cord reinforcement laid at an angle of +/-38 degree (Table 1). The materials were supplied by The Goodyear Tire & Rubber Company (Akron, OH). To avoid tension-bending coupling, the laminates were constructed with a symmetric ply lay-up. The end tabs were added to the specimens to prevent grip failures that could be experienced during mechanical testing. Coupon specimens of 19mm width were machined from these panels and edges were polished on a grinding wheel.

TABLE 1. Specifications of tire carcass composites.

Reinforcement Angle	+38, -38, -38, +38 deg
Reinforcement Composition	1260/2 nylon fibrous cord (0.33 mm radius)
Reinforcement Modulus	2.07 GPa
Reinforcement End Count	11 ends per cm width
Matrix Composition	proprietary
Matrix Modulus	5.51 MPa
Specimen Width / Thickness	19.05 mm / 5.08 mm
Gage Length	101.6 mm

In simulation of circumferential loading of a tire in the footprint region, composite coupon specimens were subjected to cyclic uniaxial tension. Cyclic testing was performed under a broad range of frequency from 2 to 30 Hz with fixed values of stress range (6.1 MPa) and minimum stress (1.5 MPa). The specimens were run until gross failure occurs. In the case of 5 Hz loading, further variation of stress range was implemented with a constant minimum stress of 1.5 MPa in order to define S-N curve. Load and displacement were measured at small time intervals during cyclic testing. Typical data acquisition consisted of 20 points per cycle and 4 cycles once every 20 seconds. Force-displacement data recorded during testing allowed for the generation of hysteresis loops for individual cycles. Fatigue testing was performed with continuous monitoring of heat generation. Temperature build-up as a function of fatigue life was recorded initially with a thermocouple attached to the specimen surface. Later the temperature was monitored using Inframetrics 525 thermography equipment. The surface temperature was measured across the width of the specimen and the image of the profile was recorded on a video system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As stated earlier, the scope of our study has been expanded to examine fracture behavior of aircraft tire carcass composites under high-frequency cyclic loading. Fatigue lifetime of composites was measured under a broad range of frequency from 2 to 30 Hz with the values of stress range and

minimum stress fixed at 6.1 and 1.5 MPa respectively. In the case of 5 Hz loading, a S-N curve was constructed by varying stress range (Figure 1). The modes of deformation and failure of composites were not affected by the use of higher frequency. As observed in the past study, angled carcass composites exhibited a high level of interply shear strain. Since the maximum cyclic stresses used in the study exceeded the fatigue endurance limit, fiber-matrix debonding was readily induced in the first cycle around the cut ends of reinforcing cords. Accompanied by the increase of cyclic strain (i.e. dynamic creep) and heat build-up, the fiber-matrix debonding was progressively worsened and developed into matrix cracking and delamination eventually leading to gross failure of the composites. Although no alteration of failure sequence was observed by the increase of frequency, the strain response and heat build-up characteristics which are indicatives of damage accumulation were found to be strongly dependent upon the level of frequency.

The process of dynamic creep undergoes three stages (Figure 2). After an initial stepwise increase in strain, the strain increases at a progressively slower rate until reaching a *steady state* at about 20% of the fatigue life. In this steady-state region, the cyclic strain increases at a constant rate and the damage takes the form of fiber-matrix debonding and matrix cracking with no delamination observed. Above 80% of the fatigue life, partial delamination appears at the specimen edge and the cyclic strain increases at a progressively higher rate eventually leading to a catastrophic failure. The increase of frequency was found to affect dynamic creep behavior in several contrasting ways: lower *initial strain*, lower *extent of dynamic creep at gross failure*, and exponentially higher *rate of dynamic creep* (Figures 2, 3 and 4). Here the extent of dynamic creep denotes the increase of displacement or strain beyond the initial instantaneous deformation. Actual values or the values extrapolated from the steady-state region were used to define the strain at gross failure. The same trend was observed in both cases. The dynamic creep rate was estimated from the slope of steady-state region.

FIGURE 1. Stress range vs fatigue life (S-N) curve for fiber-reinforced elastomer composite representing bias aircraft tire carcass (Frequency: 5 Hz)

FIGURE 2. Displacement vs time under cyclic loading: (a) 2 Hz; (b) 20 Hz (Stress range: 6.1 MPa; minimum stress: 1.5 MPa)

FIGURE 3. Dynamic creep at gross failure vs frequency (Stress range: 6.1 MPa; minimum stress: 1.5 MPa)

FIGURE 4. Dynamic creep rate in steady-state region vs frequency (Stress range: 6.1 MPa; minimum stress: 1.5 MPa)

The lower level of initial strain observed at higher frequency stems clearly from *strain rate dependence* of deformation of elastomer matrix composites. It is well-known fact that, as the rate of elongation increases, the moduli of elastomers or rigid polymers increase due to their viscoelastic nature. An increase in speed of testing is therefore similar to a decrease of temperature in influencing the modulus of elastomer matrix of composites. In high-frequency cyclic loading, higher strain rate is expected to produce initially lower strain at given cyclic stress as in the case of lower temperature. However, this trend is opposed by the effect of *hysteretic heating* as soon as cyclic loading starts. In Figure 5, the peak value of surface temperature profile across the width of coupon was plotted against the normalized time. The normalized time is defined as the time at given point divided by the time for gross failure. This figure clearly shows that the surface temperatures of composite specimens over their fatigue lives increase with higher frequency. Smaller temperature difference between the results of 20 and 30 Hz loading suggests that the state of material approaches near the onset of chemical degradation. In fact, the temperature profile of the specimens subjected to 20 and 30 Hz loading showed the lack of steady-state region and their temperature reached about 150 C (300 F) which is the cure temperature of composites.

Aside from the effect of *chemical degradation*, for some polymers in which the strength decreases with temperature, hysteretic heating could lead to so-called *thermal fatigue failure*. In addition to the decrease in strength of elastomer matrix, hysteretic heating may result in the degradation of fiber-matrix adhesion and thereby influence the process of damage accumulation in fiber-reinforced elastomer composites. It is certainly premature to speculate which degradation mechanism(s) will be responsible for the dependence of fatigue lifetime of aircraft tire carcass composites on the frequency. However, regardless of its exact nature, the involvement of material degradation process

FIGURE 5. Specimen surface temperature vs normalized time (Stress range: 6.1 MPa; minimum stress: 1.5 MPa)

was indicated by the fact that gross failure of composites requires lower value of *dynamic creep* when the frequency is increased (Figure 3). Data corresponding to 2 Hz shows deviation from the rest of frequencies tested. More testing is needed at very low frequencies to verify the trend. As shown in Figure 4, the use of higher frequency also resulted in exponentially higher *dynamic creep rate* which reflects increasingly more rapid accumulation of damage in carcass composites. When fatigue lifetime was plotted against loading frequency on a logarithmic scale in Figure 6, the least square curve fit assumed a power law relationship with an exponent of nearly -1 indicating that they are inversely proportional. In other words, fatigue life of composites is linearly proportional to the inverse of frequency i.e. the time per unit cycle.

FIGURE 6. Cycles to failure vs frequency (Stress range: 6.1 MPa; minimum stress: 1.5 MPa)

The above data suggest that the use of higher frequency results in the decrease of fatigue life of fiber-reinforced elastomer composites by simply shortening the time to reach a preset level of dynamic creep for gross failure. The extent of dynamic creep for gross failure, in turn, is lowered by increasing cyclic frequency, presumably because greater amount of hysteretic heating leads to more degradation of fiber-matrix adhesion strength or matrix strength. Although heating of the specimen is its most pronounced symptom, the amount of hysteresis itself is a fundamental parameter for expressing mechanical energy loss in a material system. In our study, the area within the hysteresis loop was used to determine directly the amount of energy loss for each composite specimen during a particular cycle. In addition to hysteresis loop area, the value of $\tan \delta$, where δ is the phase angle

difference between stress and strain, was calculated to express energy loss relative to energy stored in a material system. The following relationship was assumed: $\delta = \sin^{-1} (A/\pi \sigma_0 \epsilon_0)$ where A is the area inside the hysteresis loop, and σ_0 and ϵ_0 are the stress and strain amplitudes respectively.

Hysteresis loop area and $\tan \delta$ were measured at regular intervals throughout the fatigue life of aircraft tire carcass composites. The values are given in Table 2 for the specimens subjected to cyclic loading with different frequencies. Typical hysteresis curves under the frequencies of 2 and 20 Hz are shown in Figure 7. The values of energy loss in terms of hysteresis loop area and $\tan \delta$ were found to be relatively constant with slightly higher $\tan \delta$ at lower frequencies. According to Gehman (16), $\tan \delta$ should be in the range of 0.1 to 0.2. Dodges and Clark (17) also reported that $\tan \delta$ should decrease slightly with increasing frequency. Our results seem to be consistent with the past research and theory. The information indicates that, for load range tested, the *energy loss per cycle* does not vary noticeably with frequency. Higher frequency means greater number of loading cycles per unit time and therefore the *energy loss per unit time* becomes linearly proportional to the frequency. Since fatigue life of carcass composites is linearly proportional to the inverse of frequency, it can be postulated that the amount of energy loss per unit time i.e. the rate of energy loss determines the fatigue life of composites.

TABLE 2. Frequency dependence of mechanical loss during fatigue of tire carcass composites.

Freq	@	Hysteresis Loop Area (N-m)				Loss Tangent		$\tan \delta$	
		25%	50%	75%	99% Nf	25%	50%	75%	99% Nf
2 Hz		.462	.473	.529	.592	.128	.128	.133	.141
5		.438	.454	.458	.620	.119	.120	.121	.118
10		.467	.466	.461	.507	.117	.117	.113	.109
20		.454	.442	.457	.516	.117	.112	.114	.114
30		.553	.598	.584	.544	.118	.120	.120	.104

FIGURE 7. Hysteresis curves at 25, 50, 75 and 99 % of fatigue life: (a) 2 Hz; (b) 20 Hz (Stress range: 6.1 MPa; minimum stress: 1.5 MPa)

The facts discussed so far strongly suggest that hysteretic heating and resultant thermal degradation of materials may be dominating factors in determining the fatigue life of aircraft tire carcass composites. However, it should be noted that a much less clear correlation exists between the specimen temperature and fatigue life (Figure 5) compared with the case between the frequency and fatigue life (Figure 6). Presumably the specimen surface temperature, which this study relies on, cannot describe such critical parameters as internal heating particularly at the point of crack initiation

or true heat dissipation rate. In view of this limitation, our future study will take more rigorous approaches in measuring heat generation as well as dynamic creep under cyclic loading. Through-thickness distribution of temperature rather than nominal surface temperature will be obtained by embedding thermocouples at various locations of the specimens. Based on more accurate measurements of local strain and internal temperature, dynamic creep rate and heat dissipation rate will be redefined and correlated with fatigue life of tire carcass composites in the form of power law. By examining the frequency dependence of these power law factors, the contributions of thermal fatigue will be assessed in determining the lifetime of composites.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Our research effort has been concentrated in defining the deformation and fracture mechanisms of angle-ply fiber-reinforced elastomer composite specimens which simulate the material elements of bias aircraft tire carcass in the shoulder area. The initial goal of the study is to identify the stress, strain or temperature parameters that control the process of fatigue damage accumulation for tire carcass composites under various loading conditions. Current phase of the study was undertaken to examine tensile fatigue behavior of carcass composites under various cyclic frequencies up to the level which closely simulates loading during high-speed take-off of aircraft. As observed in our past study, angle-ply carcass composites exhibited a high level of interply shear deformation which induces fiber-matrix debonding. Accompanied by the increase of cyclic strain (i.e. dynamic creep) and heat build-up, the fiber-matrix debonding was progressively worsened and developed into matrix cracking and delamination eventually leading to gross failure of the composites. These modes of failure were not affected by the use of higher frequency.

The use of higher frequency, however, was found to affect strain response and heat build-up characteristics of composites at a given loading condition significantly. The lower level of *initial strain* observed at higher frequency stems clearly from strain rate dependence of deformation of elastomer matrix composites. This trend is opposed by the effect of hysteretic heating as soon as cyclic loading starts. As a result of hysteretic heating, the surface temperatures of composite specimens over their fatigue lives increased with higher frequency. The temperature profile of the specimens subjected from 20 to 30 Hz loading showed that hysteretic heating may lead to thermal fatigue failure as well as chemical degradation. Hysteretic heating is expected to influence both fiber-matrix adhesion strength and matrix strength. The involvement of material degradation process was indicated by the fact that gross failure of composites requires lower value of *dynamic creep* when the frequency is increased. At the same time, the use of higher frequency resulted in exponentially higher *dynamic creep rate* which reflects increasingly more rapid accumulation of damage in carcass composites. Fatigue lifetime of composites at a given loading condition was found to be inversely proportional to the frequency and linearly proportional to the time per unit cycle.

Our study revealed that the specimen surface temperature may not describe such critical parameters as internal heating particularly at the point of crack initiation or true heat dissipation rate. In view of this limitation, the amount of mechanical energy loss was directly determined from hysteresis loop for each composite specimen during a particular cycle. For load range tested, the *energy loss per cycle* was found to be nearly constant and independent of the frequency. As a result, the *energy loss per unit time* becomes linearly proportional to the frequency. Since fatigue life of carcass composites is linearly proportional to the inverse of frequency, it was postulated that the amount of energy loss per unit time i.e. the rate of energy loss determines the fatigue life of composites. Our future study plans to take more rigorous approaches in measuring heat generation as well as dynamic creep under cyclic loading.

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References

- (1) Lee, B. L., J. P. Medzorian, P. M. Fourspring, G. J. Migut, M. H. Champion, P. M. Wagner, and P. C. Ulrich, "Study of Fracture Behavior of Cord-Rubber Composites for Laboratory Prediction of Aircraft Tire Durability," SAE International Aerospace Technology Conference, Paper #901907, Long Beach, CA (1990).
- (2) Lee, B. L., J. P. Medzorian, P. K. Hippo, D. S. Liu, and P. C. Ulrich, "Fatigue Lifetime Prediction of Angle-Plied Fiber-Reinforced Elastomer Composites as Pneumatic Tire Materials," in Advances in Fatigue Lifetime Predictive Techniques (Second Symposium), ASTM Standard Testing Publication #1211, ASTM, Philadelphia, PA (1993).
- (3) Lee, B. L., D. S. Liu, M. Chawla, and P. C. Ulrich, "Fatigue Behavior of Fiber-Reinforced Elastomer Composites: I. Fracture Mechanisms and Frequency Effects," Submitted to *Journal of Materials Science*.
- (4) Personal communications with the researchers in tire industry.
- (5) Bobo, S. N., "Fatigue Life of Aircraft Tires," *Tire Science and Technology*, Vol. 16, No. 4, p.208 (1988).
- (6) Clark, S. K., "Loss of Adhesion of Cord-Rubber Composites in Aircraft Tires," *Tire Science and Technology*, Vol. 14, No. 1, p.33 (1986).
- (7) Lou, A. Y. C., and J. D. Walter, "Interlaminar Shear Strain Measurements in Cord-Rubber Composites," *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol. 18, 457 (1978).
- (8) Walter, J. D., "Cord-Reinforced Rubber," in S. K. Clark (ed.), Mechanics of Pneumatic Tires, U.S. Department of Transportation, Washington D.C. (1982).
- (9) Stalnaker, D. O., R. H. Kennedy, and J. L. Ford, "Interlaminar Shear Strain in a Two-Ply Balanced Cord-Rubber Composites," *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol. 20, p.87 (1980).
- (10) Ford, J. L., H. P. Patel, and J. L. Turner, "Interlaminar Shear Effects in Cord-Rubber Composites," *Fiber Science and Technology*, Vol. 17, p.255 (1982).
- (11) Rothert, H., B. Nguyen, and R. Gall, "Comparative Study on the Incorporation of Composite Material for Tyre Computation," in Composite Structures (Proc. of 2nd Int'l Conf. on Composite Structures, Paisley College of Technology, Scotland, UK), p.549, Applied Sci. Publ. (1983).
- (12) Cembrola, R. J., and T. J. Dudek, "Cord/Rubber Material Properties," *Rubber Chemistry and Technology*, Vol. 58, p.830 (1985).
- (13) Pagano, N. J. (ed.), Interlaminar Response of Composite Materials, Composite Materials Series Vol. 5, Elsevier Science Publ. Co., New York, NY (1989).
- (14) Breidenbach, R. F., and G. J. Lake, "Mechanics of Fracture in Two-Ply Laminates," *Rubber Chemistry and Technology*, Vol. 52, p.96 (1979).
- (15) Breidenbach, R. F., and G. J. Lake, "Application of Fracture Mechanics to Rubber Articles Including Tyres," *Philosophical Trans. Royal Soc. London*, Vol. A299, p.189 (1981).
- (16) Gehman, S. D., "Rubber Structures and Properties," in S. K. Clark (ed.), Mechanics of Pneumatic Tires, U.S. Department of Transportation, Washington D.C. (1982).
- (17) Dodges, R. N., and S. K. Clark, "Properties of Aircraft Tire Materials," SAE International Aerospace Technology Conference, Paper #881358, Anaheim, CA (1988).